

EJP SOIL

European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

Deliverable 5.1

**EU scale simulations of N₂O and other N
losses**

Due date of deliverable: M57
Actual submission date: 10.01.2025

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Project title: SIMPLE - Scenario modelling for assessing impacts of policy changes and socio-economic effects on ecosystem services of soils

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	5.1
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	EU scale simulations on N ₂ O and other N losses
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP5
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Greenhouse gas emissions and N losses
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	Jan Peter Lesschen, Wageningen Research
AUTHOR:	Jan Peter Lesschen, Chantal Hendriks, Karin Nikolaus and Kevin Duan
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14621078
LICENSE	CC BY 4.0
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	PU

ABSTRACT

One of the goals defined by the Farm to Fork strategy is to reduce nutrient losses by 50%, which would also require a reduction of the inputs of fertilizer by 20%. A modelling exercise has been carried out to quantify the benefits and trade-offs of reducing the mineral fertiliser inputs for the main arable crops at European scale. The effect on crop yield, nitrogen (N) emissions and soil organic carbon (SOC) storage is assessed when fertilizer inputs are reduced by 20%. For this modelling exercise the model MITERRA-Europe was used. This deterministic emission and nutrient flow model, calculates greenhouse gas (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) emissions, nitrogen emissions (N₂O, NH₃, NO_x and NO₃), N flows and soil organic carbon (SOC) stock changes on annual basis and at regional (NUTS2) level, using emission factors and leaching fractions. As part of WP5 the MITERRA-Europe model has been updated, with recent activity data for the year 2020 and data was collected to expand the model to Switzerland. Furthermore, the model has been extended to account for interactions between nitrogen and carbon. The RothC model that was already implemented in MITERRA-Europe has been extended to model also the effects of organic nitrogen flows, using the same approach as for carbon, but with pool specific CN ratios.

The potential yield reductions have been derived from WP3. Implementing a -20% N fertilisation will have positive aggregated effects for N losses, with on average a reduction of N₂O emissions by 15% and a reduction of the nitrogen leaching and runoff by 24%. As found in WP4 and also modelled with MITERRA-Europe, the SOC stocks decreased due to the lower crop yields and respective lower carbon inputs. However, this decrease (about 0.11 ton CO₂/ha/year) was lower compared to the average reduction in N₂O emissions (0.13 ton CO₂-eq/ha/year). Reduced mineral N fertilization will therefore have positive impacts on N losses, with net climate mitigation benefits and improvements of ground and surface water quality in the EU.

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	3
List of Tables	5
List of Figures.....	5
List of acronyms and abbreviations.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. MITERRA-Europe	7
2.1. Input data requirements	7
2.2. Soil organic carbon dynamics	7
2.3. Nitrogen dynamics	8
2.4. Implementation of the reduced mineral fertilizer scenario.....	10
3. Results	12
3.1. Development of Carbon-Nitrogen interactions	12
3.1.1 Testing and comparison of RothCN.....	13
3.1.2. Integration with MITERRA-Europe	14
3.2. Assessment of the reduced mineral fertilizer scenario.....	15
4. Conclusions.....	17
List of references	18
Appendix A Sources of input data of MITERRA-Europe	20

List of Tables

Table 1. N loss fractions to air (NH₃, N₂O, NO_x and N₂ emissions) and water (N leaching and runoff).

Table 2. Scenarios modelled by RothCN and Daisy.

Table 3. Soil average annual N mineralization (kg N/ha) simulated by RothCN and Daisy.

List of Figures

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the soil organic carbon turnover in the RothC model (Coleman and Jenkinson, 2014).

Figure 2. Schematic presentation of the calculated N flows in MITERRA-Europe (based on Velthof et al., 2009).

Figure 3. Average N input and source per crop for EU-28 countries.

Figure 4. Estimated average yield reduction due to 20% lower mineral fertilizer input for six main arable crops.

Figure 5. Schematic overview of the carbon and nitrogen pools in RothCN.

Figure 6. Soil organic C (upper panels) and N (lower panels) turnover over 200 years modelled by RothCN (left panels) and Daisy (right panels).

Figure 7. N₂O soil emissions for arable land for the baseline and the reduction scenario

Figure 8. N leaching and runoff on arable land for the baseline and the reduction scenario

List of acronyms and abbreviations

BIO	Microbial biomass
CAPRI	Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
DPM	Decomposable plant material
EJP	European Joint Programme
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm to Fork
GAINS	Greenhouse Gas and Air Pollution Interactions and Synergies
HUM	Humified organic matter
IOM	Inert organic matter
N ₂	Dinitrogen
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NH ₃	Ammonia
NO	Nitric oxide
NO ₃	Nitrate
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
RPM	Resistant plant material
SOC	Soil organic carbon
SON	Soil organic nitrogen
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The European Green Deal describes how Europe shall become the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. The Farm to Fork strategy is a central element of the Green Deal and addresses challenges related to sustainable food production and consumption. One important aim of the Farm to Fork strategy is to reduce nutrient losses by 50% as these are associated with air, soil and water pollution, loss of biodiversity and greenhouse gas emissions. This will reduce fertilization by at least 20% by 2030 (Farm to Fork). Reduced fertilization has a high potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural soils, because soil-based N₂O emissions are strongly linked to fertilization rates.

However, the CO₂ balance of soils might be adversely affected by reduced fertilization since nitrogen and carbon cycles are closely linked (Luo et al. 2006). On one hand, nitrogen is needed for sequestration of carbon in soil organic matter, but on the other hand there might also be trade-offs with higher N₂O emissions related to carbon sequestration practices (Guenet et al., 2021). Conversely, lower nitrous oxide emissions as a result of reduced fertilization rates could be associated with losses in soil carbon stocks and consequently also impair other ecosystem services including yield stability. It is therefore critical to assess potential impacts of the Farm to Fork strategy on major ecosystem services.

In the EJP Soil SIMPLE project the overall goal is to assess the impact policy changes and socio-economic effects can have on three ecosystem services of soils: yields, soil carbon storage and greenhouse gas mitigation. In WP3 the impact on crop yields has been assessed for the six main arable crops (Madenoglu et al., 2024) and in WP4 the effects of these reduced yields on soil organic carbon stock changes (Pape, 2024). The aim of this report, related to WP5 of the SIMPLE project, is to assess the impact of reduced fertilization on nitrogen losses, with a focus on N₂O emissions and N leaching and runoff. For this assessment we make use of the MITERRA-Europe model, which is a carbon and nutrient flow model for European agriculture.

2. MITERRA-Europe

The MITERRA-Europe model is used in the EJP Soil SIMPLE project to simulate the impact of reduced mineral fertilizer use on nitrogen emissions. MITERRA-Europe is a deterministic emission and nutrient flow model, which calculates greenhouse gas (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) emissions, nitrogen emissions (N₂O, NH₃, NO_x and NO₃), N and P flows and soil organic carbon stock changes on annual basis, using emission factors and leaching fractions (Velthof et al., 2009; Lesschen et al., 2011; Velthof et al., 2014). The model was developed to assess the effects and interactions of policies and measures in agriculture on N losses on a Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) 2 level in the EU-28 (Velthof et al., 2009; de Vries et al., 2011, Velthof et al., 2014). The MITERRA-Europe model was originally based on the models CAPRI (Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact, <http://www.capri-model.org>), and GAINS (Greenhouse Gas and Air Pollution Interactions and Synergies, Höglund-Isaksson et al., 2020), and was supplemented with a N leaching module, a soil organic carbon module and a module for greenhouse gas mitigation measures.

2.1. Input data requirements

The MITERRA-Europe model requires data on soil and climate, emission and leaching factors, and farm activity data (e.g., livestock numbers, manure application). In this project, the input data will be updated from 2018 to 2020, and the NUTS coding of 2016 will be updated to 2021. Besides these updates, the model extent will be extended by including data of Switzerland.

In collaboration with the Horizon Europe project [NutriBudget](#), the input data of MITERRA-Europe was updated to the most recent activity data for the year 2020. For variables that deviate each year (e.g., crop yield), an average of the years 2019, 2020 and 2021 was taken. For variables that do not have data in 2020 available, most recent data were selected. Climate data was based on the average of the period 1990-2020. Nutrient compositions of crop, organic fertilizer and chemical fertilizer composition were compiled from the median of multiple data sources. The data were all updated to the NUTS2 regions of 2021 (Eurostat, 2020). The input data and the sources that were used to obtain these input data are described in Appendix A.

Besides the update, the model would be expended to Switzerland and Turkey; countries involved in EJP Soil, but currently not covered in MITERRA-Europe. For Switzerland we were able to obtain all missing input data, or the input data were copied from Austria, but for Turkey it was unfortunately not possible to collect the required input data. Soil data were especially difficult to obtain. Turkey is not part of the European Soil Database and not included in the LUCAS soil surveys, and therefore we relied on the maps of the Soil Atlas of Asia, which are not digitized.

2.2. Soil organic carbon dynamics

The carbon dynamics in mineral soils are based on the well-established RothC-26.3 model (Coleman and Jenkinson, 2014). RothC is a dynamic soil organic carbon turnover model for mineral topsoil. The model divides soil organic carbon in four active pools: decomposable plant material (DPM), resistant plant material (RPM), microbial biomass (BIO), humified organic matter (HUM); and one inactive carbon pool: inert organic matter (IOM). Each pool has its own decomposition rate, and the IOM pool is resistant to decomposition. The decomposition rate depends on soil type, temperature, moisture content and plant cover.

Figure 2. Schematic presentation of the calculated N flows in MITERRA-Europe (based on Velthof et al., 2009).

The model assesses the soil N balance by calculating emissions, runoff and leaching. The emissions of NH₃, N₂O, NO_x are calculated as a fraction of the N inputs. The emission of N₂ is equal to the denitrification flux, which is calculated as a fraction of the N surplus. The emissions of NH₃, N₂O and NO_x and N₂ are assumed to take place in the topsoil only. The N losses to air and water depend on site properties as given in Table 1.

Table 1. N loss fractions to air (NH₃, N₂O, NO_x and N₂ emissions) and water (N leaching and runoff).

Model inputs	Assessment
NH ₃ emission fractions	<p><u>Grazing</u>: Emission factor from GAINS.</p> <p><u>Housing and manure storage systems</u>: Country-specific N emission fractions distinguished per animal type and manure type (solid and liquid) for different housing systems and manure storage.</p> <p><u>Soils</u>: Country-specific data from the GAINS model. For manure, emission fractions are distinguished between animal categories and manure type of manure (solid and liquid) and manure application technique. For fertilizer, emission fractions are distinguished between urea-based fertilizers and nitrate-based fertilizers.</p>
N ₂ O emission fractions	<p><u>Housing and manure storage systems</u>: Tier 1 approach according to IPCC 2019 guidelines</p> <p><u>Soils</u>: Two options: 1) Tier 1 approach according to IPCC 2019 guidelines (IPCC, 2019) or 2) function of N source (manure type, fertilizer type, crop residue type, grazing,</p>

Model inputs	Assessment
	mineralisation, fixation and deposition), application technique, soil type, land use and precipitation and temperature, based on Lesschen et al. (2011).
NO _x emission fractions	<u>Grazing</u> : average emission fraction at country level based on GAINS model. <u>Housing and manure storage systems</u> : 0.3% of N excretion <u>Soils</u> : EF depending on precipitation class (Velthof et al., 2014).
N ₂ emission fractions	<u>Housing and manure storage</u> : 9 x NO _x emission, i.e. 2.7% of N excretion (Oenema et al., 2007). <u>Soils</u> : set equal to denitrification rates, being equal to N surplus minus N leaching.
N leaching fractions	<u>Housing and manure storage systems</u> : fraction of N excreted in these systems that depends on the type of manure system and the type of floor (Velthof et al., 2009). <u>Soils</u> : fraction of soil N surplus (includes N input by grazing) depending on soil type, land use, soil organic content, precipitation surplus, temperature and rooting depth (Velthof et al., 2009).
N surface runoff fractions	Fraction of N input to soil by inorganic and organic fertilizers, calculated as a function of slope class, land use, precipitation surplus, soil type and depth to rock (Velthof et al., 2009).
N subsurface runoff fractions	Fraction of N leaching below the root zone, calculated as a function of soil type, moisture class and slope, derived from the IMAGE groundwater model described in Keuskamp et al. (2012).

2.4. Implementation of the reduced mineral fertilizer scenario

To simulate the scenario with reduced mineral fertilizer inputs, we had to make some changes to the model. The reduction will affect crop yield. The effect of decreasing mineral fertilizer on crop yields was estimated for the six most important arable crops in Europe (wheat, barley, maize, potato, sugar beet, and rapeseed). This work was done in WP3 and was based on national yield statistics, fertilization recommendations and fertilizer response functions (Madenoglu et al., 2024). The results from WP3 were translated into relative crop yield changes, as in MITERRA-Europe yield information is available at the NUTS2 level. The country specific relative yield changes were applied at the NUTS2 crop yields. However, in many regions crops are not only fertilized with mineral fertilizer but also receive manure as organic fertilizer. Although mineral fertilizer is the main source of N input, on average 70%, see Figure 3, the input of nitrogen from manure can be more than 50% of the total N input in some livestock dense regions.

Figure 3. Average N input and source per crop for EU-28 countries.

Therefore, we used a correction factor to compensate the yield decline because of the reduced fertilizer use based on the share of mineral fertilizer use compared to total N input from mineral and organic fertilizers. In regions without manure, the correction factor is 1 (no change), but in regions with a lot of manure the correction factor can become 0.5 or even lower for some regions. The final yield decline that was used in the model is shown in Figure 4. Rapeseed had the largest yield decline (up to 20%) whereas for the other crops the yield decline is limited to about 10%.

Figure 4. Estimated average yield reduction due to 20% lower mineral fertilizer input for six main arable crops.

For the reduced mineral fertilization we first calculated the mineral N fertilizer input per crop based on the fertilizer consumption statistics of 2020. Next, these values were reduced by 20% for the six main arable crops, while organic fertilizer input remained the same. With these adapted fertilisation values the N losses were calculated. For this study we focussed on the N₂O emissions from soils, both the direct emissions (from mineral and organic fertilizer and crop residues) and indirect emissions (N₂O emissions related to volatilization and leaching and runoff), and the N losses from nitrogen leaching and runoff.

3. Results

3.1. Development of Carbon-Nitrogen interactions

Until now, the MITERRA-Europe model has not considered the interactions between soil organic C and N. However, N mineralization and immobilization are intrinsic parts of soil organic matter turnover processes and have significant implications in soil fertility. Therefore, in a new MITERRA-Europe version currently under development, we are including a nitrogen component in the RothC module (Coleman and Jenkinson, 2014), which was already part of MITERRA-Europe. The new module is named RothCN.

RothCN is an extension of the classic RothC model, linking soil organic nitrogen (SON) turnover with soil organic carbon (SOC) decomposition using C:N ratios. For the SOC part, RothCN is mostly identical to RothC, with the modification that plant residues and manure are now considered as separate input material categories (Figure 5) to account for the different C:N ratios of these two materials. Input materials, both plant residues and manure, are partitioned into a decomposable and a resistant compartment. An additional humified manure material compartment (HMA) is assigned to hold the fraction of already decomposed manure (Figure 5). Each compartment decomposes following a first-order reaction kinetics, and is converted to microbial biomass (BIO), humus material (HUM), and CO₂, following the same principals of RothC.

To model SON turnover, each compartment is assigned a C:N ratio. Different C:N ratios may be assigned for plant residue and manure compartments to account for their differences in N content. During organic matter decomposition, N released from each compartment, and N assimilated by BIO and HUM compartments, are determined using the respective C:N ratios of the compartments. The difference between total N release and N assimilation determines whether net N mineralization or immobilization should take place. In the case of mineralization, the mineralized N is added to the soil inorganic N pool, and made available for crop uptake and soil processes (modelled by other modules of MITERRA-Europe). If immobilization should take place, RothCN will first check if the soil inorganic N pool is sufficient for immobilization requirement, and then determines if decomposition should be reduced in the case of soil inorganic N insufficiency. Therefore, with RothCN embedded in MITERRA-Europe, the SON turnover can be coupled with other N processes modelled by MITERRA-Europe, such as crop N uptake and N losses.

Figure 5. Schematic overview of the carbon and nitrogen pools in RothCN.

3.1.1 Testing and comparison of RothCN

Using the baseline scenarios established in EU project Nutri2Cycle (Duan et al., 2021), we modelled and compared the long-term turnover (200 years) of SOC/SON using RothCN and the Daisy model. Daisy is a mechanistic model that simulates the physicochemical processes of water, solute, and gas fluxes across the soil-vegetation-atmosphere interfaces (Abrahamsen & Hansen, 2000). Daisy has a soil organic matter turnover module with a compartmentalized approach similar to RothCN, and has been calibrated against long-term experiments (Bruun and Jensen, 2002). Therefore, Daisy provides a good reference benchmark to evaluate the performance of RothCN.

We selected four scenarios from Nutri2Cycle, representing dairy, pig, and arable farms in western and northwestern Europe (Table 2). The same input data were used for RothCN and Daisy, but were pre-processed differently according to model requirement (e.g., RothCN uses monthly input whereas Daisy uses daily input).

Table 2. Scenarios modelled by RothCN and Daisy.

Scenario	Country	Farming System	Input Materials
ATN-Grass	DK	Permanent grassland	Cattle slurry, grass residues
ATN-Dairy	DK	Dairy farm	Cattle slurry, crop residues
CTW-Arable	NL	Arable farm	Crop residues
CTW-Pig	NL	Pig farm	Pig slurry, crop residues

Figure 6 shows the simulated soil organic C and N turnover by RothCN and Daisy. In most cases, the overall trend in SOC/SON change over the long period are similar in both models. However, RothCN tends to estimate a larger increase or decline in SOC/SON than Daisy. Soil N mineralization simulated by the two models (Table 3) are comparable, although RothCN consistently estimated a slightly higher N mineralization in all scenarios than Daisy, which corroborates the larger decline in SON estimated by RothCN than Daisy in the CTW-Arable and CTW-Pig scenarios. These differences may be attributed to different decomposition rate parameters in the two models. Furthermore, immobilization simulated by RothCN in the test runs was not limited by soil inorganic N availability, and this could result in a higher accumulation of SON under some conditions.

Figure 6. Soil organic C (upper panels) and N (lower panels) turnover over 200 years modelled by RothCN (left panels) and Daisy (right panels).

Table 3. Soil average annual N mineralization (kg N/ha) simulated by RothCN and Daisy.

Scenario	RothCN	Daisy
ATN-Grass	460.9	451.5
ATN-Dairy	348.6	340.3
CTW-Arable	111.0	102.6
CTW-Pig	152.3	144.1

3.1.2. Integration with MITERRA-Europe

The testing and comparison of RothCN showed that it is a viable tool to model soil C and N interactions in agricultural soils. To fully integrate RothCN with MITERRA-Europe, the organic matter input to soil has to be connected to crop residue incorporation and manure application estimated by MITERRA-Europe. MITERRA-Europe already calculates C input in the organic matter, but for N it does not separate inorganic and organic forms, especially in manure. Therefore, new input parameters and calculations have to be added to estimate organic N amendments to soil. Besides, mineral N fertilisers and inorganic fraction of manure were added to soil inorganic N pool, which is made available for crop uptake and N losses. Mineralization and immobilization modelled by RothCN directly modifies the size of soil inorganic N pool. And finally, soil N surplus is recalculated based on soil inorganic N content, and losses via runoff and leaching are recalculated based on soil inorganic N surplus.

3.2. Assessment of the reduced mineral fertilizer scenario

With MITERRA-Europe a baseline simulation was performed with the activity data of the year 2020, which was compared with the simulation of the scenario in which mineral N fertilizer use per crop was reduced by 20%. The results were compared and are available at NUTS2 level and country level. Figure 7 shows the average N₂O emissions per ha for the baseline and scenario with the 20% reduction in mineral fertiliser use based on the average of the 6 crops. The highest per ha emissions are found in Belgium, Malta and the Netherlands, all countries with high nitrogen inputs from both manure and mineral fertilizer. The average reduction is about 15% varying from 7% in Cyprus to 18% in France.

Figure 7. N₂O soil emissions for arable land for the baseline and the reduction scenario.

The total emission reduction for these six crops in the EU-28 countries is 27 kton N₂O, which is 7.3 Mton CO₂-eq, based on the AR6 GWP value of 273 for N₂O. Based on the work in WP4 of the SIMPLE project the average loss of soil carbon due to the lower mineral N fertilization was about 0.11 ton CO₂/ha/year (0.928 ton C/ha over 30 years). The average reduction in N₂O emissions was 0.13 ton CO₂-eq/ha/year, which is slightly higher compared to the loss of carbon. From a climate mitigation point of view, the reduction in N₂O emissions is thus not offset by the loss of soil carbon, and as the carbon losses will decrease over time, the net climate benefit will increase.

For N leaching and runoff the results are shown in Figure 8. Also, here the N losses are highest for Belgium, Cyprus and the Netherlands. The reduction in total N leaching and runoff for these six crops was even larger and on average reduced by 24% for the EU-28. However, this varied amongst countries from 8% to 33% reduction, depending on the share of mineral fertilizer and the current N surplus. Reduced mineral N fertilization will therefore have positive impacts on N losses, with net climate mitigation benefits and improvements of ground and surface water quality in the EU.

Figure 8. N leaching and runoff on arable land for the baseline and the reduction scenario.

4. Conclusions

This study showed that a reduction in mineral N fertilisation will have positive impacts on N losses, with net climate mitigation benefits and improvements of ground and surface water quality in the EU. Although this reduction in fertilisation will likely also reduce crop yields and have a negative impact on soil organic carbon stocks, as demonstrated in the other WPs of the EJP Soil SIMPLE project, the net impact on climate mitigation is likely to be still positive with a stronger reduction in N₂O emissions compared to soil organic carbon stock losses. The results of this study are further used in the overall trade-off/synthesis assessment of WP7.

List of references

- Abrahamsen, P., and Hansen, S., 2000. Daisy: an open soil-crop-atmosphere system model, *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 15: 313-30. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-8152\(00\)00003-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-8152(00)00003-7)
- Bruun, S. and Jensen, L.S., 2002. Initialisation of the soil organic matter pools of the Daisy model, *Ecological Modelling*, 153: 291-95. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800\(02\)00017-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800(02)00017-0)
- Coleman, K. and Jenkinson, D.S., 2014. RothC-A model for the turnover of carbon in soil Model description and users guide (Windows version) (updated June 2014).
- De Vries, W., Leip, A., Reinds, G.J., Kros, J., Lesschen, J.P., Bouwman, A.F., Comparison of land nitrogen budgets for European agriculture by various modeling approaches. *Environmental Pollution* 159: 3254-3268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2011.03.038>.
- Duan, Y.F., Bruun, S., Jensen, L.S., van Gerven, L., Hendricks, C., Stokkermans, L., Groenendijk, P., Lesschen, J.P., Prado, J., and Fanguero, D., 2021. Mapping and characterization of CNP flows and their stoichiometry in main farming systems in Europe. *Nutri2Cycle Deliverable 1.5*. <https://edepot.wur.nl/547940>
- EEA, 2020. The European environment – state and outlook 2020: knowledge for transition to a sustainable Europe.
- Eurostat, 2020. Statistical regions in the European Union and partner countries: NTUS and statistical regions 2021. 2020 edition. Publications Office of the European Union. Luxembourg.
- Guenet, B, Gabrielle, B., Chenu, C., et al. 2020. Can N₂O emissions offset the benefits from soil organic carbon storage? *Glob Change Biol*. 27: 237–256. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15342>.
- Höglund-Isaksson, L., Gómez-Sanabria, A., Klimont, Z., Rafaj, P., Schöpp, W., 2020. Technical potentials and costs for reducing global anthropogenic methane emissions in the 2050 timeframe – results from the GAINS model. *Environmental Research Communications* 2: 025004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ab7457>.
- IPCC, 2013. *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.)). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp.
- IPCC, 2019. 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. Switzerland: IPCC.
- Keuskamp, J. A., Van Drecht, G., Bouwman, A.F., 2012. European-scale modelling of groundwater denitrification and associated N₂O production. *Environmental Pollution* 165: 67-76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2012.02.008>.
- Lesschen, J.P., Van den Berg, M., Westhoek, H.J., Witzke, H.P., Oenema, O., Greenhouse gas emission profiles of European livestock sectors. *Animal Feed Science and Technology* 166–167: 16-28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2011.04.058>.

Luo, Y., Hui, D. and Zhang, D., 2006. Elevated CO₂ stimulates net accumulations of carbon and nitrogen in land ecosystems: a meta-analysis. *Ecology*, 87: 53-63. <https://doi.org/10.1890/04-1724>.

Madenoglu, S., Keel, S., Kätterer, T., & Pinar, M. Ö. 2024. Creating a dataset on fertilizers and fertilization recommendations [Data set]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14244316>

Oenema, O., Oudendag, D., Velthof, G.L., 2007. Nutrient losses from manure management in the European Union. *Livestock Science* 112: 261-272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livsci.2007.09.007>.

Pape, B. (2024). Europe scale simulation of reduced fertilization scenarios. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14069147>

Tanneberger, F., Tegetmeyer, C., Busse, S., Barthelmes, A. and 55 others. 2017. The peatland map of Europe." *Mires and Peat* 19(22): 1-17.

Velthof, G.L., Oudendag, D., Witzke, H.P., Asman, W.A.H., Klimont, Z. and Oenema, O., 2009. Integrated Assessment of Nitrogen Losses from Agriculture in EU-27 using MITERRA-EUROPE. *J. Environ. Qual.* 38: 402-417. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2008.0108>.

Velthof, G.L., Lesschen, J.P., Webb, J., Pietrzak, S., Miatkowski, Z., Pinto, M., Kros, J., Oenema, O., 2014. The impact of the Nitrates Directive on nitrogen emissions from agriculture in the EU-27 during 2000–2008. *Science of The Total Environment* 468–469: 1225-1233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.04.058>.

Appendix A Sources of input data of MITERRA-Europe

Besides N, P, and C, the MITERRA-Europe model can also assess the nutrient and heavy metal dynamics of Cu, S, Mg, Ca, Cu, Zn.

Parameter	Datasets	Source
Soil pH, CEC, availability of CaCO ₃ , NPK content	Soil Chemical properties at European scale based on LUCAS 2009/2012 topsoil data	Ballabio, C., Lugato, E., Fernández-Ugalde, O., Orgiazzi, A., Jones, A., Borrelli, P., Montanarella, L. and Panagos, P., 2019. Mapping LUCAS topsoil chemical properties at European scale using Gaussian process regression. <i>Geoderma</i> , 355: 113912.
Soil organic carbon (SOC) content, S, Mg, Ca	LUCAS 2018 TOPSOIL data	Fernandez-Ugalde, O; Scarpa, S; Orgiazzi, A.; Panagos, P.; Van Liedekerke, M; Marechal A. & Jones, A. LUCAS 2018 Soil Module. Presentation of dataset and results, EUR 31144 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-54832-4, doi:10.2760/215013, JRC129926. Orgiazzi, A., Ballabio, C., Panagos, P., Jones, A., Fernández-Ugalde, O. 2018. LUCAS Soil, the largest expandable soil dataset for Europe: A review. <i>European Journal of Soil Science</i> , 69(1): 140-153. https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12499 .
Zn, Cu, Cd	Zn and Cu: LUCAS 2009 dataset; Cd: GEMAS dataset	Zn : Van Eynde, E., Fendrich, A. N., Ballabio, C., & Panagos, P. 2023. Spatial assessment of topsoil zinc concentrations in Europe . <i>Science of The Total Environment</i> , 892 , 164512. Cu : Ballabio, C., Panagos, P., Lugato, E., Huang, J.-H., Orgiazzi, A., Jones, A., Fernández-Ugalde, O., Borrelli, P., Montanarella, L. 2018. Copper distribution in European topsoils: An assessment based on LUCAS soil survey . <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , 636 : 282-298. Cd: Birke, M., Reimann, C., Rauch, U., Ladenberger, A., Demetriades, A., et al., 2017. GEMAS: Cadmium distribution and its sources in agricultural and grazing land soil of Europe — Original data versus clr-transformed data. <i>Journal of Geochemical Exploration</i> 173: 13-30. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gexplo.2016.11.007 .
Soil texture, coarse fractions, bulk density, rooting depth	Topsoil physical properties for Europe (based on LUCAS topsoil data)	Ballabio C., Panagos P., Montanarella L. Mapping topsoil physical properties at European scale using the LUCAS database (2016) <i>Geoderma</i> , 261 , pp. 110-123.
Fertilizer use and type	FAOSTAT and IFASTAT	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 1997. FAOSTAT statistical database. Rome: FAO. International Fertilizer Association, 2024, https://www.ifastat.org/ .
Percentage and area of natural grassland (not fertilized land) and rough grazing, animal numbers, crop areas, crop yields,	EUROSTAT and Agrarstrukturhebung (2020) for Germany	European Commission, 2020. Eurostat statistical database. Brussels: European Commission. Agrarstrukturhebung, 2024, https://www.regionalstatistik.de/genesis/online?operation=pr

arable farm size, farming system, crop rotation, livestock units, areas with organic farming, irrigation, crop cover (arable land), perennial grass cover (used for C balance)		vious&levelindex=0&step=0&titel=Statistik+%28Tabellen%29&levelid=1727099952945&acceptscookies=false.
N excretion of animals, CH ₄ emissions from manure management and enteric fermentation	National GHG inventory submissions	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2020. National Inventory Submissions 2020. Bonn: United Nations Climate Change.
Precipitation, evapotranspiration, temperature	ERA5	Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Rozum, I., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Dee, D., Thépaut, J.-N. (2023): ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), DOI: 10.24381/cds.adbb2d47 (Accessed on 10-09-2024).
Precipitation surplus, surface runoff and groundwater leaching fractions	Keuskamp et al. (2012)	J. A. Keuskamp, G. Van Drecht, A. F. Bouwman (2012). European-scale modelling of groundwater denitrification and associated N₂O production. Environmental Pollution, 165, pp. 67-76, doi: http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2012.02.008.
Soil type, soil texture class, soil depth, rooting depth, soil erosion, organic carbon class, parent material, peat fraction.	ESDB v2.0 and soil erosion maps (JRC)	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, 2018. The GAINS model. Laxenburg: IIASA
Slope	EU-DEM	European Environmental Agency, 2024. European Digital Elevation Model (EU-DEM). DOI: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/digital-elevation-model/eu-dem#Slope (Accessed on 01-08-2024).
C-factor, erosion	USLE model	Panagos, P., Borrelli, P., Meusburger, C., Alewell, C., Lugato, E., Montanarella, L., 2015. Estimating the soil erosion cover-management factor at European scale . Land Use policy journal. 48C, 38-50.
N ₂ O, CO ₂ (peatland) emission factors, global warming potentials,	IPCC	IPCC, 2019. Update of 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Volume 4, Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use. IPCC National Greenhouse Gas Inventories Programme.
NH ₃ emission factors, NH ₃ mitigation measures	GAINS	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, 2018. The GAINS model. Laxenburg: IIASA.
Soil cover and Tillage practice	FSS	European Commission, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/microdata/farm-structure-survey
Areas under derogation	EC	European Commission, https://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/water-nitrates/index_en.html
Composition of organic fertilizers	(-)	Multiple sources based on literature and database study

Composition of crop (residues)	(-)	Multiple sources based on literature and database study
Composition of chemical fertilizers	(-)	Multiple sources based on literature and database study, including expert judgement of Römken (2024)
Ca, Cd, Cu, K, Mg, Na, NH ₃ , NO _x , SO _x , Zn deposition	EMEP	Van Loon, M., Tarrasón, L., Posch, M., 2005. Modelling Base Cations in Europe. EMEP/MS-CW&CCE Note2/2005. ISSN 0804-2446.
Land use	CORINE Land Cover - 2018	European Union, Copernicus Land Monitoring Service 2021, European Environment Agency (EEA). Corine Land Cover. DOI: CORINE Land Cover 2018 (vector/raster 100 m), Europe, 6-yearly — Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (Accessed on 01-08-2024).
Base cation weathering	ESDB v2.0 and De Vries (1991)	De Vries, W. 1991, Methodologies for the assessment and mapping of critical loads and of the impact of abatement strategies on forest soils, DLO Winand Staring Centre, Wageningen, the Netherlands, Report 46, 109 pp.

